

Exploring the Role of Digital Surveillance in Economic Growth: A Sentiment Analysis of Companies Across Key Sectors

Dr. Anuradha Mishra¹, Dr. Neetu Goel², Dr. Pooja Thakar³

¹Mass Communication, VIPS-TC, GGSIPU

²Information Technology, VIPS-TC, GGSIPU

³Information Technology, VIPS-TC, GGSIPU

Abstract— The study explores the complex relationship between digital surveillance and economic growth across various sectors, including e-commerce, fintech, edutech, agritech, and manufacturing. Through the lens of surveillance capitalism, the paper investigates how behavioural data collection and AI-powered analytics influence consumer behaviour, organizational productivity, and broader economic outcomes. With empirical case studies from Amazon, UPI, PhysicsWallah, Country Delight, and Adani Group the research identifies trends in customer satisfaction, security challenges, and the economic ripple effects of data-driven optimization by employing sentiment analysis on publicly available datasets. While digital surveillance fosters economic opportunities by enhancing operational efficiency, market reach, and customer targeting, it simultaneously raises critical ethical and legal concerns related to privacy, data misuse, and trust erosion. The paper underscores the need for a balanced approach—leveraging surveillance for development while reinforcing robust data protection policies and digital rights frameworks.

Keywords— Digital Surveillance, Economy, Security Challenges, Sentiment Analysis, Data Protection

I. INTRODUCTION

Surveillance giants like Google, Facebook, and similar tech companies have become deeply intertwined with the fabric of modern life, exerting subtle yet profound control over individuals and societies. These companies operate under a model widely described as surveillance capitalism, where every facet of human experience—searches, clicks, posts, location data, even off-platform behaviors—is harvested as free raw material for data extraction. Unlike traditional business models, these platforms convert user behaviors into behavioral data, most of which users are unaware they are producing.

This behavioral surplus is then processed using sophisticated algorithms to create powerful prediction products. These products forecast not only what we might buy, but also how we think, move, and even vote, and are sold to advertisers or other entities interested in influencing our future actions. Over time, the constant collection and commodification of personal data leads to the normalization of what was once considered abnormal—that is “the pervasive tracking of minute personal details”. Users have become desensitized to data collection practices that, just a decade ago, would have caused public outrage.

Moreover, surveillance is not limited to information that users knowingly share—such as profile details or posts—but extends much further: tracking browsing habits, location history, conversations, and even associations with friends and family. This pervasive surveillance reaches well beyond voluntary disclosure, shaping behaviors, nudging decisions, and ultimately redefining notions of privacy and autonomy in the digital age. Through these processes, surveillance giants mold public discourse, commercial preferences, and even aspects of identity, often without users’ informed consent or understanding.

This research study will explore the transformative role of digital surveillance in driving economic growth across five key sectors: ecommerce, manufacturing and infrastructure, agri-tech, banking and finance, and startups. By focusing on how the collection of behavioral data and the use of AI-powered analytics influence consumer behavior, organizational productivity, and overall economic outcomes, the study will

provide valuable insights into the synergy between technology and economic development. Case studies from each sector will highlight how digital tools enable businesses to optimize operations, enhance customer experiences, and create new market opportunities, ultimately fostering growth and innovation in the digital age.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research has examined various aspects of digital surveillance, including AI-driven productivity analytics, digital capitalism, authoritarianism, and ethical implications etc. As noted by Grisold et al. (2024), advancements in information technology have enabled organizations to track, quantify, and analyze employee behaviors at unprecedented granularity and scale, leading to what is termed behavioral visibility. This digital turn in surveillance is marked by the ubiquity of sensors, biometrics, and algorithmic analytics, extending the scope of monitoring well beyond traditional forms. Within organizations, digital surveillance now manifests through diverse modalities—ranging from keystroke logging and location tracking to AI-driven productivity analytics (Grisold et al., 2024; Bali et al., 2025). Modern workplaces, as demonstrated in case studies from Punjab, India (Bali et al., 2025), employ a suite of tools (CCTV, biometric attendance, data analytics, GPS) justified by the dual imperatives of security and efficiency.

Surveillance Capitalism (Zuboff, 2019) and *Digital Authoritarianism* (Polyakova & Meserole, 2019) further extend understanding beyond the organizational sphere. Surveillance, they argue, is not only a managerial or security apparatus but also a mode of capital accumulation, enabling the commodification of behavioral data and influencing both governance and market dynamics.

Digital Surveillance may contribute towards economic progress through various means like reducing the crime rate and ensuring public safety to ensure a more favourable environment for investment and tourism. Investment in surveillance infrastructure further ensures a welcoming environment for commercial activity (Raza, 2023). Digital Surveillance ensures business optimization and productivity. Employee activities can be monitored more effectively, leading to increased accountability and output

Meta-analytic studies (Liao & Li, 2021; Chang & Lee, 2020) report that excessive or opaque surveillance can erode trust, induce stress, reduce job satisfaction, and foster resistance among employees. Conversely, when surveillance systems are transparent and participatory, negative impacts are attenuated—a finding corroborated across cultural contexts, including the Punjab workplace survey.

Legal and normative inquiries (Nishnianidze, 2024) highlight persistent gaps in regulations governing privacy and digital rights, particularly in emerging economies and hybrid regimes where surveillance is justified under the rhetoric of modernization and security. Despite global efforts to enshrine legal identity and data protection (e.g., World Bank ID4D reports), marginalized populations remain at heightened risk of exclusion or misuse.

Research Gap: The existing literature highlights significant gaps in understanding the precise relationship between digital surveillance and economic growth, particularly in diverse regional contexts. There is lack of empirical evidence on research directly linking surveillance intensity to economic outcomes. China's model is well studied; there is less attention to the post-Soviet states like central Asia. In this context the existing study will help in understanding the surveillance -economy nexus. In addition there is a need to understand longitudinal studies tracing the long-term developmental effects of surveillance adoption on economic variables.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

To interrogate the entanglement of digital surveillance and economic growth, the paper is guided by the following research questions:

RQ1. How is Digital surveillance evolving across different domains, specifically ecommerce, Agri-Tech, Edu-Tech, Banking and Industries.

RQ2. In what ways does Digital surveillance influence the behaviour of economic stakeholders including customers, entrepreneurs and Industry?

IV. DIGITAL SURVEILLANCE MEANING AND DEFINITION

Digital Surveillance is the mechanism through which various entities like government, corporations and organisations use digital tools to monitor, track, and analyse the information related to people's communication, behaviour, and interaction without their knowledge or consent. Digital surveillance, the widespread monitoring of activities and data through electronic devices, has become a pervasive feature in both private and professional spheres in the digital age. Organizations increasingly adopt digital surveillance tools, including biometric systems, internet usage tracking, CCTV, GPS-enabled devices, and productivity monitoring software, to gain insights into human behavior. AI-driven monitoring systems, facial recognition, and keyloggers further augment these capabilities, providing unprecedented access to information. Governments also leverage such technologies for various purposes, from maintaining public safety to economic development. Some of the digital surveillance methods include (Sable, 2025):

- Monitoring electronic communication includes Intercepting and analysing emails, text messages, and social media posts.
- GPS Tracking uses location data from smartphones and other devices that tracks individuals' movement by identifying the patterns and behaviour of the individual
- Facial recognition technology which employs software to identify and track individuals in public spaces.

Various companies across different sectors have adopted a combination of aforementioned digital surveillance techniques to obtain the data of the consumer behaviour. It has helped the companies to strategies their market segmentation and mold the individual behaviour to a potential consumer.

V. CASE STUDIES

The study examines the role of digital surveillance in driving economic growth across five key sectors—commerce, manufacturing and infrastructure, agri-tech, banking and finance, and startups. It incorporates case studies from selected companies, including Amazon, UPI, PhysicsWallah, Country Delight, and the Adani Group, to explore how behavioural data collection and AI-powered analytics shape consumer behaviour, enhance organizational productivity, and influence broader economic outcomes. Using sentiment analysis on publicly available datasets, the research highlights trends in customer satisfaction, identifies security challenges, and assesses the economic ripple effects of data-driven optimization.

Case-1 E- Commerce :Amazon

Amazon is the American international e-commerce company which was initiated by Jeffrey P Bezos in 1994. It entered the Indian Market in the year 2013. Since then, Amazon is the most preferred online brand for the respondents across India, as per the Nielsen Media report Conducted by Amazon in September 2023 (TOI, 2024). Some of the Amazon e-commerce start-ups are pets.com, audible.com, Junglee.com, IMBD.com, Zappos.com, Woot etc. The Target customers of Amazon are middle- and upper-class people who are techno savvy and have less time to purchase goods physically. To reach customers in villages and remote areas a local store is provided the internet facility where people may reach to place their order online and the customers may receive their order from the same local store (Wadhwa, Vashisht, & Sohi, 2017). Amazon has consistently increased its revenue in the last five years from 386.06 billion to 638.96 billion (2020-2024).

Amazon has a very good Customer Relation Management system (CRM). It has its own CRM software which accurately captures customer previous purchase data and helps in streamlining their shopping journey. Through CRM customers may track their previous purchase data and track their order without any human interaction. CRM is constantly gathering information through customer browsing, searching and data mining etc. It has a good customer interface where orders can be placed and the payment may be done through the personal account of a customer on Amazon. However, there are personal data of the customer which is available to Amazon that could be an important issue of digital surveillance (Hayaton, 2020).

Case-2 Banking and Finance :Unified Payments Interface (UPI)

It played a pivotal role in India's digital transformation. In the year 2016 National Payments Corporation of India (NCPI) launched UPI. This system of digital payment has integrated the multi bank accounts into a single mobile application. Through schedule payment requests this mechanism helps in providing the benefit of seamless fund transfer, peer to peer transaction and merchant payment. This process has made the financial transaction fast and effortless. In 2023 there were 11.40 billion transactions which reached 16.58 billion transactions in 2024. Around 632 banks are linked to this platform. UPI had played an important role in pushing the Indian economy towards a cashless economy.

During the COVID-19 pandemic people found UPI a safe system to make the payment as it was a contactless transaction in comparison to the cash transaction. There has been innovation in this system with adoption of payment apps which requires a QR code to make the payment to the individual account. In India the UPI had a significant impact on the various sections of the society like small business, street vendors and migrant workers.

India's digital payment making revolution through UPI is gaining global acceptance. In recent times UPI has operated in seven countries namely, UAE, Singapore, Bhutan, Nepal, Sri Lanka, France, and Mauritius (PIB, 2024). This digital payment system has undeniably empowered citizens, expanded economic opportunities, and played a key role in strengthening India's growing presence in the global financial landscape.

Despite its widespread adoption and convenience, UPI continues to grapple with significant security challenges. In FY24, UPI fraud cases witnessed a sharp 85% increase, rising from 7.25 lakh incidents in FY23 to 13.42 lakh. The total value involved in these cases also nearly doubled, surging from ₹573 crore to ₹1,087 crore (CNBCTV18, 2024). Some of the Top UPI payment frauds doing rounds in India include (Aggarwal, 2021):

- **Deceptive UPI Identifiers**– Many fraudsters create deceptive UPI handles that mimic official names such as NPCI, UPI, or BHIM, tricking users into revealing their account details via fake UPI apps, ultimately leading to financial fraud.
- **Request Money fraud** – Many fraudsters exploit unaware users by falsely claiming that scanning a QR code and entering a UPI PIN is needed to receive money, thereby tricking them into authorizing fraudulent transactions.
- **Remote Screen Monitoring Frauds** - A large number of unverified apps available on the Google Play Store can gain access to sensitive data on users' phones. These apps can extract financial information, significantly heightening the risk of UPI-related fraud.
- **Phishing Attacks** - Fraudsters often send malicious links via emails or SMS. When users click on these unauthorized links, it can lead to data breaches and financial fraud.

Case-3 EduTech Sector – Case Study on PhysicsWallah

PhysicsWallah (PW) was founded in 2016 by a teacher “Alakh Pandey “ from a very humble background. It has grown from a YouTube channel to a \$3.7 billion unicorn Company by 2025 (startup talk published on 05 May 2025 by Sakshi Jadhav, Sanvi Barjatya, <https://startuptalky.com/prateek-maheshwari-success-story/>). PW’s YouTube channel has over 13.6 million subscribers, which provides free lectures, study notes, and exam tips for Engineering and Medical Competitive Exams along with Secondary and Senior Secondary curriculum. This drives organic traffic for marketing without any heavy promotional spending. It enables PW to scale without the financial strain that competitors face. PW has also powered artificial intelligence through its Alakh AI platform that was launched in 2023. Moreover, it delivers personalized, scalable education that adapts content based on a student’s progress and weaknesses, answer common queries reducing dependence on human educators, provide insights into student’s performance, enabling targeted interventions. This addition supports India’s NEP 2020, which emphasizes AI-driven education and digital learning. YouTube minimizes marketing costs yet insures high trust due to Freemium Content. AI reduces educator costs. Low-bandwidth apps address rural India’s access thus enhancing market growth. Social Media Engagement is equally important in this digital era, PW is active on X to address criticisms and share updates thus maintaining positive sentiment. Leverages user-generated content (e.g., testimonials) to amplify reach. PhysicsWallah’s (PW) marketing strategy is lean, student-centric, and highly effective, leveraging organic channels to minimize customer acquisition costs (CAC) and build trust, thus helping in paramount growth as seen in the last 10 years.

Case-4 Adani Groups

Over the last five years, the Adani Group has emerged as a powerhouse of economic activity in India, marked by explosive financial growth, strong operational momentum, and ambitious expansion plans. It has transformed into a diversified conglomerate with strategic investments across infrastructure, energy, transport, and sustainability—underpinned by robust financial management and continued capital deployment into future-focused sectors.

Case-5 Startup : Country Delight

Established in 2013 by IIM Indore alumni Chakradhar Gade and Nitin Kaushal, Country Delight has grown into one of India’s leading direct-to-consumer (D2C) dairy brands. The company delivers fresh, natural, and unadulterated milk straight to urban households, combining quality with doorstep convenience.

What began as a five-member team has now expanded to over 1,000 employees nationwide, with revenue soaring 100x since inception and achieving an annual run rate of over USD 50 million.

Country Delight differentiates itself through flexible subscription plans, affordable influencer-led promotions, and a referral program that rewards customers with credit points—fueling strong organic, word-of-mouth growth.

The brand has invested significantly in enhancing its mobile app, enabling customers to:

- Set fixed recurring delivery schedules for milk and other dairy products.
- Track pending orders in real time.
- Rate products and share feedback directly with farmers.
- Earn rewards through referrals.

By leveraging digital marketing channels and collaborating closely with macro and micro-influencers, Country Delight connects effectively with its core urban audience. Its approach shows that building trust and ensuring convenience can go hand in hand, with technology and transparency driving long-term loyalty.

The Final Take

The study explores how digital surveillance and AI-driven analytics fuel economic growth across five sectors—e-commerce (Amazon), banking & finance (UPI), edutech (PhysicsWallah), infrastructure (Adani Group), and D2C startups (Country Delight).

Across all cases, data collection and behavioural analysis have enabled personalization, operational efficiency, market expansion, and stronger customer engagement:

- Amazon leverages CRM and purchase history tracking to boost sales, though raising privacy concerns.
- UPI has revolutionized payments and gone global, but faces rising fraud risks.
- PhysicsWallah uses AI to personalize learning, reduce costs, and reach rural students.
- Adani Group applies analytics to optimize large-scale infrastructure, energy, and transport operations.
- Country Delight tracks orders, preferences, and feedback to refine service and grow organically.

While these strategies drive rapid growth and economic opportunity, they also bring challenges around data privacy, cybersecurity, and ethical use of surveillance technologies.

VI. ANALYSIS & RESULT

Analysis is done on multiple data sets obtained from various domains such as ecommerce, Agri-tech, Edu-tech, e-wallet etc. to understand how digital marketing backed by digital surveillance impacts the consumer behavior. Data is collected and sentiment analysis is done to understand the behavior of customers and how it impacts economies.

Case 1: Ecommerce- Amazon

Dataset: Data is obtained from Kaggle, that contains Amazon Product’s Ratings and Reviews on various categories of products. Data is pre-processed and transformed to majorly focus on Short and Long Reviews of the products with total records of 1466.

Sentiment Analysis is done with the help of NLTK in Python to find out the positive, negative and neutral distribution on Amazon Products in the category (electronics, office products, toys and games, home improvement, health and personal care). Figure 1 showcases the graph on customer sentiment distribution with 94 % positive, 5 % negative and less than 1% neutral. This clearly represents how digital marketing backed up by digital surveillance leads to a satisfied customer base and hence boost economic growth for the company. Figure 2 showcases the Yearly Average Stock Price of the Company in the last 5 years. Tremendous growth is visible in the last two years.

Figure 1 Showcases the Graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution

Figure 2 showcases the Yearly Average Stock Price of the Company in the last 5 years

Case 2: e-wallet- Paytm

Dataset: Data is obtained from Google web scraping with the help of reddit in python. Data is pre-processed and transformed to majorly focus on Customer Comments and Reviews with total records of 2783. Sentiment Analysis is done with the help of NLTK in Python to find out the positive, negative and neutral distribution on comments and reviews by people. Figure 3 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution with 49 % positive, 22 % negative and 27% neutral. Figure 4 showcases the Yearly Average Stock Price of the Company in the last 5 years. Tremendous growth was visible last year.

```
positive 49.424874
neutral 27.965492
negative 22.609633
Name: sentiment, dtype: float64
```


Figure 3 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution

Figure 4 showcases the Yearly Average Stock Price of the Company in the last 5 years.

Case 3: Edu-tech- Physics Wallah

Dataset: Data is obtained from Google web scraping with the help of reddit in python. Data is pre-processed and transformed to majorly focus on Customer Comments and Reviews with total records of 205.

Sentiment Analysis is done with the help of NLTK in Python to find out the positive, negative and neutral distribution on comments and reviews by people. Figure 5 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution with 58 % positive, 21 % negative and 20% neutral. Customer Satisfaction is quite significant in the study.

```

positive    58.333333
negative    21.078431
neutral     20.588235
Name: sentiment, dtype: float64
    
```


Figure 5 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution

Case 4: Adani Group of Industries

Dataset: Data is obtained from Google web scraping with the help of reddit in python. Data is pre-processed and transformed to majorly focus on Customer Comments and Reviews with total records of 1200. Sentiment Analysis is done with the help of NLTK in Python to find out the positive, negative and neutral distribution on comments and reviews by people. Figure 6 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution with 27 % positive, 9 % negative and 63% neutral. Customer seems to reflect a neutral state for Adani Industries.

```

neutral     63.052544
positive    27.522936
negative     9.424520
Name: sentiment, dtype: float64
    
```


Figure 6 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution

Case 5: Agri-tech – Country Delight

Dataset: Data is obtained from Google web scraping with the help of reddit in python. Data is pre-processed and transformed to majorly focus on Customer Comments and Reviews with total records of 1436. Sentiment Analysis is done with the help of NLTK in Python to find out the positive, negative and neutral distribution on comments and reviews by people. Figure 7 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution with 48 % positive, 12 % negative and 38% neutral. Customers seems to be satisfied with the products of Country Delight and hence boost the economy and customer base with organic marketing strategies. Figure 8 showcases the Yearly Average Stock Price of the Company in the last 5 years. Tremendous growth is visible in the last one year.

```
positive    48.639218
neutral     38.520586
negative    12.840195
Name: sentiment, dtype: float64
```


Figure 7 showcases the graph on Customer Sentiment Distribution

Figure 8 showcases the Yearly Average Stock Price

VII. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION AND POLICY GUIDELINES

The ethical consideration with respect to digital surveillance requires the consideration of the Individual privacy. In the Putta swamy case the petitioner challenged the Adhar case involving issue of ID card. In this case privacy goes beyond the confines of article 21. The court judgement recognized the importance

of data protection, informational self – determination and data sovereignty. The court also recognized that it is not only essential to have the right to privacy against the state but also the private players. Following the Puttaswamy judgment, the IT Act, 2000 classifies the disclosure of information contained in any electronic record, book, or similar source without the person's consent as a punishable offence. In addition, fraudulent financial activities are to be taken into account. The 2006 amendment to the IT Act introduced Sections 43A and 72A. The Section 43A mandates the implementation of reasonable security practices for safeguarding Sensitive Personal Data or Information (SPDI) and holds entities liable to pay compensation for any wrongful loss or gain resulting from negligence. SPDI includes financial details such as bank account information, credit card numbers, and passwords. In addition, Section 2 of the Data Protection Bill extends its applicability to both government and non-state actors. The Bill addresses provisions concerning data fiduciaries, social media intermediaries, special categories of personal data, and sensitive personal data of children, as well as regulations on data localisation and cross-border data transfers. Besides this, the ethical issues of concern also raises the issues related to algorithmic fairness, security of data collection and worker and consumer autonomy.

The policy guidelines must ensure the legal compliance framework which requires regular legal audits for compliance. There is a need to Introduce mandatory SIAs before implementing large-scale surveillance. It includes assessing privacy impact, societal implications, and economic and cost benefit. Moreover there is a need to Involve civil society, academic experts, and industry in developing sector-specific surveillance policies. In addition, it is required to create centralized Data Ethics Boards in organizations and government agencies to oversee surveillance data use.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Digital surveillance has emerged as a double-edged sword in the contemporary economic landscape. On one hand, it drives innovation, improves service delivery, enhances customer experiences, and contributes to economic growth, as evidenced by sectoral case studies in e-commerce, finance, edutech, and agritech. The use of AI and data analytics enables organizations to tailor their offerings, optimize productivity, and scale efficiently. On the other hand, the normalization of continuous monitoring—often without informed consent—raises profound concerns about autonomy, data sovereignty, and privacy.

The analysis reveals a clear positive correlation between consumer sentiment, company performance, and the strategic deployment of surveillance-backed digital tools. However, the ethical and legal vacuum surrounding data governance in emerging economies must be addressed to prevent exploitation and loss of public trust. The study emphasizes the urgent need for transparent, participatory, and rights-based surveillance frameworks, particularly in regions where legal safeguards remain underdeveloped.

In sum, digital surveillance can significantly contribute to economic progress when aligned with inclusive governance, ethical norms, and strong regulatory mechanisms. Future research should focus on long-term, cross-regional studies that quantify the developmental impact of surveillance technologies while keeping human dignity and democratic accountability at the forefront.

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